

HIKARI: A POSITIVE ENERGY BUILDING WITH AN ARCHITECTURALLY INTEGRATED PV FACADE AND A PV ROOFTOP SYSTEM (190 KWP)

Gaiddon, B.¹, Valentin, M.², Alfonsi, L.³, Laquerriere, M.L.⁴, Gouranton, G.⁵, Corgier, D.⁶

¹Hespul, 14 place Jules Ferry, 69006 Lyon, France

email: bruno.gaiddon@hespul.org

²SPL Lyon-Confluence, 73 rue Smith, 69002 Lyon, France

email: mvalentin@lyon-confluence.fr

³Bouygues Immobilier, 186 Avenue Thiers, 69006 Lyon, France

email: l.alfonsi@bouygues-immobilier.com

⁴Tecsol, 20, Boulevard Eugène Deruelle, 69003 Lyon, France

email: mll@tecsol.fr

⁵Terre Ciel Energies, 2, allée du Parc Montaury, 64600 Anglet, France

email: germain.gouranton@terrecielenergies.com

⁶Manaslu, Savoie Technolac, 73370 Le Bourget-du-Lac, France

email: david.corgier@cmdl.pro

ABSTRACT: In the center of the Lyon-Confluence district in Lyon, France, the public company in charge of the redevelopment of the area, SPL Lyon-Confluence, launched in 2011 an international design competition for the selection of a real estate developer to build a positive energy building on a 3.400 m² piece of land called P plot.

The team Bouygues Immobilier/SLC in association with Kengo Kuma from Japan has been selected by the jury for the design of a group of 3 buildings called HAKARI with dwellings, offices places and shops for a total floor area of 12.300 m². In order to build a positive energy building to respect the requirements set by SPL Lyon-Confluence, the selected team decided to equip this building with 2 kinds of PV systems: a see-through PV facade on the MINAMI building (21 kWp) and a rooftop PV system on the roof of each of the 3 buildings (168 kWp). The official opening ceremony of this building took place on Thursday 17 September 2015.

Keywords: Solar Architecture, Building Integrated PV (BIPV), Building Integration, Façade

1 INTRODUCTION

Lyon-Confluence is the name of an urban project started in 2003 that aims at redeveloping a former industrial area of 150 ha in the city center of Lyon and building 1.000.000 m² of new dwellings, offices and shops by 2030.

This project has also very ambitious targets in terms of sustainability that are described in a sustainable action plan design with WWF within the One Planet Living initiative [2]. One of the most ambitious goals set in this action plan is the zero carbon objective defined as follow: the 1 million m² of floor area of new buildings to be built in the area by 2030 should not lead to any increase of the CO₂ emissions of the area.

In order to reach this goal, SPL Lyon-Confluence, the public company in charge of the redevelopment of the area, has undertaken several concrete measures to:

- Drastically reduce the consumption of new buildings in the area,
- Refurbish the existing buildings of the area located in the north of the district,
- Massively install, on almost each new block, renewable energy systems such as wood chip boilers, solar thermal systems and PV systems.

This article provides information on the most recent building that has been delivered in this area: a positive energy building of 12.300 m².

2 FEASIBILITY STUDY

In 2009, SPL Lyon-Confluence selected the team Herzog & de Meuron (architects/urban planners) from Switzerland and MDP - Michel Desvigne (landscaper) from France to design the second phase of the Lyon-Confluence project. This team released in December 2009 the masterplan for the redevelopment of the former

wholesale market and, in September 2010, the feasibility study of a new block called P Block.

The P Block is a central element of the Lyon-Confluence project, even if the area of this piece of land is smaller than other blocks with around 3 380 m² (91m x 37m). It is surrounded by the Ice-Rink to the north, the water place and quai Antoine Riboud) on the south to the east by the Cours Charlemagne, the main street of Lyon-Confluence with the tram line, just in front of the Leisure Centre and the Rhône-Alpes region Headquarters (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: location of the P block at the corner water place / tram line

Herzog & de Meuron proposed that this block, as most blocks of the area, should have multiple functions (offices, dwellings and shops) and gave an estimation of the floor area potential of the building to be built on this piece of land:

- 7.000 to 8.000 m² of offices,
- 3.000 to 4.000 m² of dwellings,

- 1.000 to 1.500 m² of shops.

Herzog & de Meuron then proposed several possible building shapes with the same expected floor area per usage that can be foreseen on this plot (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: example of possible shape proposed by Herzog & de Meuron (offices in purple, dwellings in yellow and shops in orange)

3 INTERNATIONAL DESIGN COMPETITION

SPL Lyon-Confluence was in charge of organising an international competition to select the developer that will be in charge of the design and construction of the P Block building within the Lyon-Confluence area.

Based on the feasibility study done by Herzog & de Meuron for this piece of land, SPL Lyon-Confluence and its assistants, the Environmental engineering office TRIBU and Hespul, set up the environmental and energy targets of this building. Thanks to the financial support expected within the EC funded project NEXT-Buildings related to very low energy buildings [3], the energy performance requirements of this building were more ambitious than what was achieved for recent buildings of this area and was set at a very strict level: make the P Block building a positive energy building.

More precisely, this objective was defined as the following: the positive energy balance of the plot over the year shall consider the whole energy consumption (and not only the heating consumption) and shall be calculated with the yearly primary energy consumption and the yearly primary energy produced by the building (see Figure 3)

Figure 3: Definition of the positive energy target

This energy performance target and the primary energy factors to be used (3.2 for electricity and 0.2 for biomass) have been included in the environmental guidelines used for the international competition to select a developer for the design and the construction of this

building.

The first round of this international competition was launched on January 2011 by SPL Lyon-Confluence and was quite successful since 17 teams composed of developers, architects, engineering offices and environmental consultants applied to this bid. It took then 3 months for SPL Lyon-Confluence to analyze the applications and to short-list 4 teams of developers for the second round of the competition:

- ALTAREA-COGEDIM (Developer) with Bernard Reichen, Barbosa & Guimaraes (Architects),
- BOUYGUES Immobilier/SLC (Developer) with Kengo Kuma/CBR Architectes (Architects),
- ICADE (Developer) with Shigeru Ban/Rue Royale Architectes (Architects)
- VINCI (Developer) with Dominique Perrault/Mateo Arquitectura (Architects)

This time, each team had to pre-design a building and to send a comprehensive report on the architecture features and the energy performance assessment of the building.

SPL Lyon-Confluence received from each selected team building proposals with high quality architecture and very low energy needs so that it was not easy for the jury to select one of them. After a full audit of the application report and an oral presentation of each project, the jury decided, in September 2011, to award the proposal lead by Bouygues Immobilier/SLC in association with Kengo Kuma.

4 DESIGN PHASE

The awarded project proposed by Bouygues Immobilier/SLC is called HIKARI, which means natural light in Japanese. It is composed of 3 buildings for a total floor area of approx. 12.300 m²:

- HIGASHI (East), an office building with shops on the ground floor,
- MINAMI (South), in the middle of the plot, an apartment building with 36 dwellings and shops on the ground floor,
- NISHI (West), 3060 m² with 5 storeys of offices and 4 top-end penthouse apartments on the 2 upper storeys and shops on the ground floor (see Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Figure 4: The 3 buildings of the HIKARI project: HIGASHI on the right, MINAMI in the middle and NISHI on the left

The design team was composed of the following companies:

- Project developers: Bouygues Immobilier and SLC Pitance,
- Architect: Kuma Associates Europe,
- Contractor: SETEC Bâtiment,

- PV engineering: Tecsol,
- Energy consultant: Manaslu Ing.

Figure 5: Virtual image of the Southern façade of the HIKARI building

4 PV SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 Overall energy strategy

The design of a positive energy building requires to strongly focus on energy systems in order to produce on site and with renewable energy sources the energy necessary to operate the building. Thus, in order to provide electricity, heat and cold to the building, the design team decided to use 3 kinds of renewable energy sources available on site, which are solar, biomass and ground water, with 3 main energy systems which are solar PV modules, a cogeneration system (CHP) and an absorption chiller (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Overview of the energy system design

The HIKARI building is in fact equipped with 2 kinds of PV systems:

- A see-through PV façade on the MINAMI building,
- A rooftop PV system on the roof of each of the 3 buildings.

The technical details of these PV systems, which have been designed in partnership with Toshiba as a supplier, are given below.

4.2 See-through PV façade

The see-through PV façade has a power of 21 kWp and is used as balcony for the dwellings of the MINAMI building and is highly visible from the street and from the inside of the flats. Consequently, the design team paid special attention to its design and to safety issues.

As Kengo Kuma, the architect of this building, decided to design an organic building with cuttings in the façade in order to improve natural light inside the building, he also tried to avoid the use of regular PV modules and designed 9 different layouts of PV modules that give the impression of random positioning of PV cells (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Drawing of 6 PV façade elements out of the 9 available layouts

The quality of the backside of PV modules is also an important issue since, in case of see-through PV façade, this becomes one element of the dwelling inside design. Thus, the design team selected high quality mounting technics based on a bolted glazing façade with custom-made metal supports and no visible DC wires (see figure 8).

Figure 8: artist impression of the back side of the PV façade from the inside of a dwelling

As this see-through PV façade is also used as balcony, an approval of the mounting technique of the PV façade by an accredited and independent body was necessary.

First, a prototype of the see-through PV façade was installed for one flat of the MINAMI building during summer 2014.

Then, a comprehensive set of tests done by a testing laboratory and among them the M50/900J test that consists in smashing the PV façade with a 50 kg sand bag from a height of 1,2 m in order to create a chock of 900 Joules according to the NFP 01-012 standard with P 08-302 testing protocol (see Figure 9). All these tests have been successful so the PV façade was approved for safety on September 2014.

Figure 9: M50/900J chuck test on the PV module

Detailed features of the see-through PV façade are:

- Cells: 1120 x Neo Solar Power NP6 multi crystalline cells (5” – 3,8 W)
- PV modules: AGC SunEwat / thickness of 21,6 mm / 9 different layouts
- Mounting technic: Bolted glazing façade with custom-made metal supports
- Inverters: 3 x SMA Tripower – 18,5 kVA in total
- Expected yield: 15 MWh/year

4.3 Rooftop PV system

The rooftop PV system has a power of 168 kWp and covers almost all the roof area of the 3 buildings (HIGASHI, MINAMI and NISHI) and has also an aesthetical role as it has been designed to give a homogenous appearance to the roof surface, as it is visible from surrounding hills.

Detailed features of the rooftop PV system are:

- PV modules: 700 x Panasonic HIT-N240 (240 Wp)
- Mounting technique: custom-made metal frames - tilt angle: 10° - east-west
- Inverters: 13 x SMA Tripower – 143 kVA in total
- Expected yield: 182 MWh/year

Figure 10: Rooftop PV system of HIKARI

5 ACHIVEMENTS

HIKARI is now completed and the official opening ceremony took place on Thursday 17 September 2015.

The current PV market in France concentrates on low cost and/or rural systems. High quality and customized systems, such as the see through PV modules, in metropolitan areas are an exception.

With its central location in Lyon, the high visibility of the PV façade and its excellent design quality, HIKARI is a new BIPV show-case. All technical details of this building are available in the deliverable D5.1 of the NEXT-Buildings project “Report on the P Plot overall construction process” [4]. A comprehensive

monitoring campaign is now about to start. First results of the operation of this building and its PV system will be available at the end of 2016.

Figure 11: HIKARI building in La Confluence area in Lyon (September 2015)

Figure 12: Detail view of the see-through PV façade

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